

THE ROLE OF THE EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT IN FORMING VALUES IN STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

In the interpretation of moral values, classical pedagogues, scientists who conducted research in the field of psychology, and modern pedagogical methodological approaches play an important role. It is worth noting that national traditions, mentality and customs also serve as a rich source for the formation of moral concepts in the minds of young people.

In higher education institutions, teachers must perform several tasks in terms of moral education. The first task is to set a personal example. Because if there is a discrepancy between the words of the teacher and his actions, conflicts may arise in the student's perception of moral values. The second task is to present moral education more through practical cases, real-life examples, and scientific and practical projects than through short lectures. The third task is to develop a plan for continuous spiritual and educational work at the institute, university, or faculty level to introduce moral values. Here, all employees, from the leadership of the educational institution to dormitory teachers, should work in a single system. The level of formation of moral values in students is also measured by the initiatives that arise from within them. For example, students can show how attentively they have accepted moral values through the student union, various clubs, or community work. When young people voluntarily participate in charity events, environmental activities, or community work, it means that they have a sense of moral responsibility. This process also serves as a certain indicator for educators. Because it makes it possible to understand how the moral concepts presented during theoretical lessons are perceived by students in practical life.

In the interpretation of moral values, classical pedagogues, scientists who conducted research in the field of psychology, and modern pedagogical methodological approaches play an important role. It is worth noting that national traditions, mentality and customs also serve as a rich source for the formation of moral concepts in the minds of young people.

Reveals the nature of educational values, which are oriented towards the social and personal factor. It is desirable that social values, including educational values, also serve to form a person, increase his dignity, ensure the recognition of the personal factor by educators as a leading subject of educational processes, help him develop free and independent thinking, as well as social activity skills. Consequently, the need to educate and bring up a well-rounded

person and a qualified specialist acquires even more urgent meaning and essence in the current conditions, when new social relations are being established.

Academician R.Kh.Djuraev noted that in organizing education, it is important not to force students, but to approach the work creatively, taking into account the individual characteristics of each student, to organize socio-political, educational work in a purposeful manner, to be an example for them in every work, to understand the demands and needs of society, to achieve strict adherence to discipline, to apply theoretical knowledge in practice, to care when necessary, to study experience and traditions, national and universal values, and to use them effectively and creatively in their future profession. Initially, in order to reveal the intellectual potential of students, it is necessary, first of all, to completely change the attitude towards their professional activities along with professional knowledge. We believe that teaching technological subjects should be carried out in accordance with pedagogical ethics, taking into account the level of knowledge of students. This, in turn, largely depends on the pedagogical and psychological principles of teaching and the pedagogical skills of teachers. The effectiveness of this process changes the attitude towards education in teaching technological subjects.

The issue of developing national values among students of higher educational institutions is gaining relevance in the current era of globalization. National values are an important factor in the holistic upbringing of a person, in the formation of such qualities as social responsibility, patriotism, historical memory and respect for cultural heritage. The results of the study show that pedagogical and psychological approaches play an important role in the formation and strengthening of national values in the minds of students. National values can be effectively conveyed to students through modern educational methods, interactive approaches, interdisciplinary integration and innovative technologies. At the same time, these values are formed more deeply and sustainably through a person-centered approach, the development of emotional intelligence, and the creation of a positive psychological environment. Practical experience shows that spiritual and educational events, projects and creative activities encourage students to have a positive attitude towards national values. Therefore, the development of national values in the higher education system should remain one of the priority areas of state policy. This, in turn, ensures spiritual upliftment, stability, and continuity of cultural heritage in society.

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